

Toward Single Plant Digital Twin via 3D Plants Reconstruction and Segmentation

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Abstract—With the advent of Precision Agriculture we are going in the direction of a fourth agricultural revolution. In the future, crop works will be entirely automated by intelligent machines that will carry out all operations, from sowing to harvesting, leading to more efficient use of resources (like water and nutrients) and contamination reduction via a fine-tuned spraying of pesticides. One of the requirements for agricultural machines to accomplish in-field localized operations is to have a digital model of each single crop plant. This framework leads to the idea of *Plant Digital Twin*, that is, the computerized counterpart of a real plant. With this in mind, we developed a system that can scan crop rows reconstructing and distinguishing individual plants. The final goal is growth monitoring and treatments targeted to the needs of each specific plant.

Index Terms—Plant Phenotyping, Digital Twin, Precision Agriculture, Agriculture 4.0, Agricultural Robotics.

I. THE NEED FOR AUTONOMOUS PLANT PHENOTYPING

World crop production is required to double by 2050 to satisfy the increase of food demand determined by a rapidly increasing human population [1]. To improve crop performance, breeders and biologists require phenotyping data, i.e., the measurements of relevant indices about plant growth and health. For instance, biologists can rely on *Plant Phenotyping* to quantitatively measure how a new high-yielding genotype of crops could interact with the environment [2]; or, farmers can exploit phenotyping data as the input of technologies like variable-rate spraying of water, targeted nutrients delivery, and on-demand pesticides distribution. However, nowadays, plant phenotyping is performed manually by skilled scientists or breeders; this procedure is laborious, expensive, and time-consuming.

Automatic plant phenotyping systems aim at overcoming the limitations of current manual methods, by measuring the morphometric and physiological parameters of plants in a rapid, non-destructive, accurate, and high-throughput manner. Morphometric parameters include plant height, stem diameter, leaf area, leaf angle, stalk length, and in-plant space, while physiological parameters are, e.g., chlorophyll, photosynthetic rate, water stress, biomass, salt resistance, and leaf water content [3].

Even if considerable work has been done, we are still at the beginning of the journey toward a robust and standard phenotyping methodology [2]. One of the major flaws in the current methodologies is the incapability to collect, reliably,

and in situ, large scale phenotyping measurements. In addition to the management of huge quantity of phenotyping data, new modeling techniques, advanced analysis tools, and prediction models are necessary to turn automatic phenotyping into a real-world reality [4].

Recently, in [5], the authors developed a semi-autonomous ground vehicle capable of scanning crop rows at the level of each single plant, reconstructing the 3D model of the plants through a stereo camera and collecting environment data like temperature, humidity, and light intensity. However, single plant recognition relies on RFID tags placed on each of them, thus requiring extensive human labor. Moreover, the scanning process needs the robot to stop at every single plant, hindering actual high-throughput phenotyping. Instead, Mueller et al. [6], developed an autonomous ground vehicle capable of collecting phenotyping data with passive and contact-based sensors. Employing a 2D LiDAR in push-broom configuration, they reconstructed the entire field. However, they did not perform single plant segmentation. Moreover, the localization approach only relies on an RTK-GPS (plus an AHRS sensor) that is not always a reliable means of localization.

In this paper, we present a novel phenotyping method that processes data collected by an easy-to-install custom platform, and builds a 3D digital model, for each single plant. As for the Digital Twin in Industry 4.0, we present here a first step toward the Plant Digital Twin in Agriculture 4.0, where each plant will have a digital counterpart with its story, its current status, its expected performance.

II. PLANT RECONSTRUCTION AND SEGMENTATION

To overcome the limitations of current phenotyping robotic platforms, we developed a system able to scan entire crop rows and to recognize single plants (see in Figure 1). Our platform is constituted by a set of sensors and it can be mounted on different platforms like an autonomous robot or a tractor. We choose the following minimal set of sensors able to provide a good trade-off among amount of data, cost, power-consumption and richness of information: a 2D LiDAR, two RGB-D cameras, a GPS, an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU). The LiDAR sensor has been mounted in push-broom fashion, that is, the laser scan plane is vertical relative to the ground. The two RGB-D cameras are parallel to both sides of the crop row. The system is able to localize itself thanks to a

Fig. 1. Our platform mounted on a custom four-wheels tray.

sensors fusion approach of the GPS, the IMU and cameras information. The localization approach could work even in the total absence of GPS information, thus relying only on camera images with the Visual Odometry.

The 3D model of the plants is reconstructed fusing both the RGB-D cameras and the 2D LiDAR data. The cameras reconstruction has the advantage of color information but at the expense of capturing only the upper part of the plants due to a restricted Field Of View. The advantage of LiDAR reconstruction is the higher accuracy and coverage since it perceives from the ground to the top leaves.

The reconstruction process exploits the localization information from the sensor fusion approach. LiDAR laser scans are merged in a single point cloud one after the other knowing the relative transformation of the sensor origin to the base position of the robot. The cameras color and depth images are registered one to the other into the final point cloud by a graph-based Simultaneous Localization And Mapping (SLAM) approach.

The LiDAR data are used as input of the segmentation algorithm since trunks positions are exploited to find single plants. The data structure underlying 3D reconstructions is the point cloud. Once the LiDAR has collected a point cloud, it passes through a pipeline constituted of the following steps (see video at <https://youtu.be/OU1R911CYx8>): (i) the point cloud is filtered from far and low-intensity points, outliers, and ground points (ii) the plants are sectioned from the ground level to a certain height to isolate the lower parts of the trunks and support poles (iii) trunks and poles are clustered and their centroids are computed (iv) the point cloud is projected on the ground plane and the variance of the projected points laying into a fixed-radius circle around each centroid is computed; the circles with low variance are poles, so their points are filtered out (v) the filtered point cloud is clustered by K-means algorithm given as initial k centroids the trunks centroids (vi) each resulting cluster corresponds to a plant and bounding box is placed around it (Figure 2).

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

We tested our method on a dataset we collected at a botanical garden in Milan. We manually pulled through the row a cart supporting our sensor system. We performed multiple scans over time with the purpose to track and recognize

Fig. 2. A section of vineyard row with the segmented plants surrounded by bounding boxes

each single plant. By visual inspection, we can state that the reconstructions represent with accuracy the scanned subjects in terms of shape, colors, and scale. The reconstructions quality depends on localization accuracy.

Our approach has demonstrated to work even in the partial absence of the GPS signal. The localization algorithm showed progressively decreasing accuracy passing from offline to real-time computation. The segmentation approach has correctly segmented most of the plants. However, as we assume the lower part of a point cloud containing only trunks or poles, the algorithm could be misled by some grass bushes.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

In this paper we proposed a first step toward the autonomous phenotyping of single plants by an autonomous mobile robot. In the near future we expect autonomous physical agents and smart sensors collecting data on the field and participating in building 3D georeferenced models of entire crops at the level of single plant. The model will evolve as more passages throughout the crop are performed.

Having a digitalized plant, i.e., its Digital Twin, will allow us to monitor and follow it during its entire life giving birth to a new concept that is the agricultural counterpart of the Internet of Things, the Internet of Plants. Think about the potential of a network of plants that share information. What if an infested plant could alert its neighbors to receive treatments hence blocking a pest diffusion?

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